

Performance of rice under intermediate deepwater conditions in response to methods of sowing and interplant cultivation after establishment. Cuttack, India, 1990.

Treatment	Seedling emergence (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Methods of sowing				
Broadcasting	225	123	1.9	8.2
Line sowing (drilling)	240	137	1.9	8.0
Hill sowing (dibbling)	232	135	1.9	8.9
SE ±	—	4	0.1	0.2
LSD (P = 0.05)		12	ns ^a	0.8
Post-establishment cultivation				
No cultivation (control)		144	2.0	8.6
Interplant cultivation with hand hoe		138	2.0	9.5
Beushaning		113	1.7	6.9
SE ±		4	0.1	0.2
LSD (P = 0.05)		12	0.2	0.8

^aNonsignificant.

Water accumulated in the field gradually after germination. It was 20 cm at 30 DE, 50 cm at 90 DE, and 62 cm at 120 DE (panicle initiation) and 150 DE

(milk grain). It receded gradually to near zero at crop maturity in mid-Dec.

The effect of interaction between sowing method and post-establishment

cultivation on rice growth and yield was not significant. The crop germinated and established equally well under different sowing methods because of good monsoon rains within a week of planting (see table). Plants from broadcast seed had fewer panicles/m² than line-sowed plants. Weeds were not a serious problem. Interplant cultivation did not affect grain yield, but significantly improved straw yield compared with the control.

Beushaning significantly decreased panicles/m² and thus grain yield by 15.4% and straw yield by 19.7%. The uprooted plants established poorly. Stagnant water in the field further hampered tillering. Beushaning under intermediate DWR conditions does not appear to improve productivity as it does under shallow water conditions. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effects of fungicides, insecticides, and their interaction on sheath rot (ShR) severity

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ShR, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw., is associated with rice mealybug *Brevnesia rehi* Lindinger in Tamil Nadu. We conducted greenhouse and field experiments to study the effect of various fungicides, insecticides, and their

interactions on ShR severity.

Three IR20 seedlings/pot were maintained in insect-proof cages in a greenhouse trial. Three mealybug crawlers that had been soaked for 15 min in *S. oryzae* (10⁷ conidia/ml) spore suspension were placed inside the sheath that encloses the young panicle to inoculate tillers at booting stage.

Various pesticides or pesticide combinations were sprayed after 8 h (see table). Treatments of about 50 seedlings each were replicated four times in a completely randomized block design. We assessed disease severity 15 d after ShR symptoms first appeared on control plants.

IR20 seedlings were transplanted into 40 m² plots and spaced at 20 × 15 cm in the field trial. At booting stage, all tillers within 1 m² of each plot's center were inoculated with mealybug crawlers. Treatments were the same as in the greenhouse. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Disease severity was randomly assessed 10 d before harvest on 20 seedlings/m² plot. Grain yield from individual m² plots was estimated at harvest.

Greenhouse and field experiment results showed that tridemorph + phosphamidon protected rice against ShR better than tridemorph alone. Yield greatly increased compared with that of the untreated control (see table). □

Effect of various pesticides on ShR severity.^a

Treatment	Disease intensity ^b		Mean yield (t/ha) in field	Yield increase over control (%)
	Greenhouse experiment	Field experiment		
Tridemorph 0.1%	3.8 c	2.5 b	5.3 c	63.3
Carbendazim 0.1%	5.3 f	4.0 c	4.5 e	40.2
Phosphamidon 0.03%	4.7 e	4.9 d	5.0 d	53.6
Neem oil 10%	8.6 g	8.7 e	3.8 f	16.8
Tridemorph 0.1% + phosphamidon 0.03%	1.0 a	0.5 a	6.6 a	105.4
Tridemorph 0.1% + neem oil 10%	2.5 b	2.4 b	6.1 b	87.6
Carbendazim 0.1% + phosphamidon 0.03%	2.5 b	2.7 b	6.2 b	91.7
Carbendazim 0.1% + neem oil 10%	4.6 de	4.1 b	4.9 d	51.3
Neem 10% + phosphamidon 0.03%	4.1 cd	5.3 d	5.1 d	56.5
Control (water spray)	9.0 g	9.0 c	3.2 g	—

^aMeans in a column followed by different letters show significant difference at 5% level by DMRT. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0–9.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.